

Intercept probability analysis in DF time switching full-duplex relaying network with impact of Co-channel interference at the eavesdropper

Pham Minh Nam¹, Phu Tran Tin², Minh Tran³

¹Faculty of Electronics Technology, Industrial University of Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

²Wireless Communications Research Group, Faculty of Electrical and Electronics Engineering,
Ton Duc Thang University, Vietnam

³Optoelectronics Research Group, Faculty of Electrical and Electronics Engineering,
Ton Duc Thang University, Vietnam

Article Info

Article history:

Received Aug 10, 2019

Revised Feb 25, 2020

Accepted Mar 18, 2020

Keywords:

Co-channel
Energy harvesting
Full-duplex
Interference
Outage probability

ABSTRACT

In this research, we propose and investigate intercept probability analysis in DF time switching relaying full-duplex with impact of Co-channel interference at the eavesdropper. In the beginning stage, we present the DF time switching relaying full-duplex with the Impact of Co-channel interference at the eavesdropper. Furthermore, the closed-form expression of the intercept probability (IP) is analyzed and derived in connection with the primary system parameters. Finally, the Monte Carlo simulation is performed for verifying the correctness of the analytical section. From the research results, a novel solution and some recommendations can be proposed for the communication network in the near future.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Phu Tran Tin,
Wireless Communications Research Group,
Faculty of Electrical and Electronics Engineering,
Ton Duc Thang University, Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam.
Email: phutrantin@tdtu.edu.vn

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, wireless-powered communication has gained considerable interest because of its capability to deal with the energy scarcity in energy-constrained wireless networks. An attractive solution that overcomes the above limitation is to harvest energy from human-made radio frequency (RF) electromagnetic radiation (also known as wireless power transfer) [1-6]. Based on that fact, the WPCN and its efficiency are considered as the main research direction in the communication network. In [7], the authors investigated the fundamental tradeoff between the rate of transporting a commodity between one point and another. Furthermore, practical receiver designs for simultaneous wireless information and power transfer is detail studied in [8]. Moreover, the energy harvesting (EH) communication network with the partial network-level cooperation was proposed and investigated in [9]. Authors in [10] presented the cognitive relay networks with the EH and information transmission (IT) at the same time. Moreover, the TSP and PSP protocols in the EH communication network and the performance comparison between them are investigated in [11-15].

In this research, we propose and investigate Intercept Probability (IP) Analysis in DF time switching Relaying full-duplex with Impact of Co-channel Interference at the eavesdropper. The main contribution of this paper can be drawn as the follows;

- The DF time switching Relaying full-duplex (FD) with the Impact of Co-channel Interference at the eavesdropper is proposed and investigated.
- The exact and asymptotic analysis of the system IP is derived and investigated in connection with the primary system parameters.
- The Monte Carlo simulation is conducted for verifying the correctness of the analytical analysis.

In this paper, the system model of the communication network has considered in second section. The IP analysis is presented in the third section in detail. Numerical results and some conclusions is drawn in the fourth sections. In the final section, some conclusions are proposed.

2. SYSTEM MODEL

In this section, Figure 1 proposed the DF time switching relaying full-duplex (FD) with the Impact of Co-channel interference at the eavesdropper. The energy harvesting (EH) and information transferring (IT) phases are drawn in Figure 2 [16-20].

Figure 1. System model

Figure 2. The EH and IT phases

2.1. Energy harvesting (EH) phase

During the first phase, the received signal at the relay can be given by:

$$y_r = h_{sr}x_s + n_r \tag{1}$$

The average transmitted power at the relay can be obtained as:

$$P_r = \frac{E_h}{(1-\alpha)T} = \frac{\eta\alpha TP_s |h_{sr}|^2}{(1-\alpha)T} = \kappa P_s |h_{sr}|^2 \tag{2}$$

2.2. Information transmission (IT) phase

In the second phase, the received signal at the relay can be given by

$$y_r = h_{sr}x_s + h_{rr}x_r + n_r \tag{3}$$

where h_{rr} is the loopback interference channel and $E\{|x_r|^2\} = P_r$. The received signal at the eavesdropper can be expressed as:

$$y_E = h_{RE}x_r + \sum_{n=1}^M x_{I_n} h_{I_n E} + n_E \tag{4}$$

where h_{RE} is the relay to the eavesdropper channel gain, n_E is AWGN with variance N_0 and $h_{I_n E}$ is the channel gain between n^{th} interference source and eavesdropper. We assume that all the interferences source have the same transmit power P_I , it mean that $E\left\{\left|x_{I_n}\right|^2\right\}_{n=0\dots M} = P_I$. From (4), the signal to noise ratio (SNR) at the eavesdropper can be given as;

$$\gamma_E = \frac{|h_{RE}|^2 P_r}{P_I \sum_{n=1}^M |h_{I_n E}|^2 + N_0} \quad (5)$$

Substituting (2) into (5), (5) can be rewritten as;

$$\gamma_E = \frac{\kappa P_s |h_{sr}|^2 |h_{RE}|^2}{P_I \sum_{n=1}^M |h_{I_n E}|^2 + N_0} = \frac{\kappa \Psi |h_{sr}|^2 |h_{RE}|^2}{\Omega \sum_{n=1}^M |h_{I_n E}|^2 + 1} = \frac{\kappa \Psi X}{\Omega Y + 1} \quad (6)$$

where $\Psi = \frac{P_s}{N_0}$, $\Omega = \frac{P_I}{N_0}$, $X = |h_{sr}|^2 |h_{RE}|^2$ and $Y = \sum_{n=1}^M |h_{I_n E}|^2$

2.3. Remark 1

The probability density function (PDF) of random variable (RV) Z can be obtained as

$$f_Y(t) = \frac{(\lambda_3)^M}{(M-1)!} t^{M-1} \exp(-\lambda_3 t) \quad (7)$$

where λ_3 is the mean of RV Y .

3. INTERCEPT PROBABILITY (IP) ANALYSIS

3.1. Exact analysis

The IP can be defined by;

$$IP = \Pr(\gamma_E > \gamma_{th}) \quad (8)$$

substituting (6) into (8), the IP can be reformulated as (9).

$$\begin{aligned} IP &= \Pr\left(\frac{\kappa \Psi X}{\Omega Y + 1} > \gamma_{th}\right) = 1 - \Pr\left(\frac{\kappa \Psi X}{\Omega Y + 1} \leq \gamma_{th}\right) \\ &= 1 - \int_0^{\infty} F_X\left[\frac{\gamma_{th}(\Omega y + 1)}{\kappa \Psi}\right] \times f_Y(y) dy \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Next, the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of X can be computed as (10).

$$\begin{aligned} F_X(x) &= \Pr(|h_{sr}|^2 |h_{RE}|^2 < x) = \Pr\left(|h_{sr}|^2 < \frac{x}{|h_{RE}|^2}\right) \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} F_{|h_{sr}|^2}\left(\frac{x}{a} \mid |h_{RE}|^2 = a\right) \times f_{|h_{RE}|^2}(a) da \\ &= 1 - \lambda_1 \int_0^{\infty} \exp\left(-\frac{\lambda_2 x}{a}\right) \times \exp(-\lambda_1 a) da \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Here the (10) can be rewritten as the following;

$$F_X(x) = 1 - 2\sqrt{\lambda_1\lambda_2x} \times K_1\left(2\sqrt{\lambda_1\lambda_2x}\right) \quad (11)$$

applying (7) and (11), (9) can be obtained by;

$$IP = \frac{2(\lambda_3)^M}{(M-1)!} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1\lambda_2\gamma_{th}}{\kappa\Psi}} \int_0^\infty y^{M-1} \times \exp(-\lambda_3y) \times \sqrt{(\Omega y + 1)} \times K_1\left(2\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1\lambda_2\gamma_{th}(\Omega y + 1)}{\kappa\Psi}}\right) dy \quad (12)$$

3.2. Asymptotic analysis

At the high SNR regime ($\Psi \rightarrow \infty$), (6) can be calculated by (13).

$$\gamma_E^\infty \approx \frac{\kappa\Psi X}{\Omega Y} \quad (13)$$

The IP can be computed as (14).

$$IP^\infty = 1 - \Pr\left(\frac{\kappa\Psi X}{\Omega Y} \leq \gamma_{th}\right) = 1 - \int_0^\infty F_X\left(\frac{\gamma_{th}y\Omega}{\kappa\Psi}\right) \times f_Y(y) dy \quad (14)$$

Using the results from (7) and (11), the IP can be rewritten by (15).

$$\begin{aligned} IP^\infty &= \frac{2(\lambda_3)^M}{(M-1)!} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1\lambda_2\gamma_{th}\Omega}{\kappa\Psi}} \int_0^\infty y^{M-1} \times \sqrt{y} \times \exp(-\lambda_3y) \times K_1\left(2\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1\lambda_2\gamma_{th}y\Omega}{\kappa\Psi}}\right) dy \\ &= \frac{2(\lambda_3)^M}{(M-1)!} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1\lambda_2\gamma_{th}\Omega}{\kappa\Psi}} \int_0^\infty y^{M-1/2} \times \exp(-\lambda_3y) \times K_1\left(2\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1\lambda_2\gamma_{th}y\Omega}{\kappa\Psi}}\right) dy \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

By letting $t = \sqrt{y}$, (15) can be reformulated as;

$$IP^\infty = \frac{4(\lambda_3)^M}{(M-1)!} \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1\lambda_2\gamma_{th}\Omega}{\kappa\Psi}} \int_0^\infty t^{2M} \times \exp(-\lambda_3t^2) \times K_1\left(2t\sqrt{\frac{\lambda_1\lambda_2\gamma_{th}\Omega}{\kappa\Psi}}\right) dt \quad (16)$$

applying eq (6.631,3) of table of integral [21], finally the IP can be claimed by;

$$IP^\infty = \frac{\exp\left(\frac{\lambda_1\lambda_2\gamma_{th}\Omega}{2\kappa\Psi\lambda_3}\right)}{(M-1)!} \times \Gamma(M) \times \Gamma(M+1) \times W_{-M, \frac{1}{2}}\left(\frac{\lambda_1\lambda_2\gamma_{th}\Omega}{\kappa\Psi\lambda_3}\right) \quad (17)$$

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we investigate the influence of the primary system parameters on the IP of the system model [22-27]. As shown in Figure 3, the system IP increases with a rising of ψ from 0 to 25 dB. From Figure 3, the system IP increases while ψ varies from 0 to 25 dB. Here we set system parameters as $\gamma_{th}=0.5$, $\eta=0.8$, $\alpha=0.5$, $\Omega=10$ dB, and $M = 1.3$. Besides, the asymptotic curve is near the exact curve. The effect of Ω on the system IP is drawn in Figure 4 with $M = 2$, $\eta=0.8$, $\alpha=0.5$, $\Omega=10$ dB, and $\psi=5$ dB. As shown in Figure 4, the system IP has a huge decrease with the rising of Ω . In Figures 3 and 4, we can state that the simulation and analytical values are the same to convince the analytical section.

Furthermore, the effect of α and M on the system IP are investigated in Figures 5 and 6. In Figure 5, we set $M = 2$, $\gamma_{th}=0.5$, $\eta=0.5$, 0.8 , $\psi=\Omega=5, 10$ dB and in Figure 6, we set $\gamma_{th}=0.5$, $\eta=0.8$, $\alpha=0.5$, $\Omega=5, 10$ dB. From these Figures, the system IP has a huge increase with the rising of α and has a huge decrease while M

varies from 1 to 10. These results show that the analytical curve is the same as the simulation curve to verify the correctness of the analytical analysis.

Figure 3. IP versus ψ

Figure 4. IP versus Ω

Figure 5. IP versus α

Figure 6. IP versus M

5. CONCLUSION

In this research, we propose and investigate IP Analysis in DF time switching Relaying FD with Impact of Co-channel Interference at the eavesdropper. In the beginning stage, we present the DF time switching Relaying FD with the Impact of Co-channel Interference at the eavesdropper. Furthermore, the closed-form expression of the IP is analyzed and derived in connection with the primary system parameters. Finally, the Monte Carlo simulation is performed for verifying the correctness of the analytical section.

REFERENCES

- [1] Bi S., Ho C. K., Zhang R., "Wireless powered communication: Opportunities and challenges," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 117-125, 2015.
- [2] Niyato D., Kim D. I., Maso M., Han Z., "Wireless Powered Communication Networks: Research Directions and Technological Approaches," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 2-11, 2017.
- [3] Yu H., Lee H., Jeon H., "What is 5G? Emerging 5G Mobile Services and Network Requirements," *Sustainability*, vol. 9, no. 10, pp. 1-22, 2017.
- [4] Zhou X., Zhang R., Ho C. K., "Wireless Information and Power Transfer: Architecture Design and Rate-Energy Tradeoff," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 61, no. 11, pp. 4754-4767, 2013.

- [5] Nguyen T. N., M. Tran, D. H. Ha, T. T. Trang, and M. Voznak, "Multi-source in DF Cooperative Networks with the PSR Protocol Based Full-duplex Energy Harvesting over a Rayleigh Fading Channel: Performance Analysis," *Proceedings of the Estonian Academy of Sciences*, 2019.
- [6] Nguyen, Tan N., Minh Tran, Thanh-Long Nguyen, Duy-Hung Ha, and Miroslav Voznak, "Performance Analysis of a User Selection Protocol in Cooperative Networks with Power Splitting Protocol-Based Energy Harvesting Over Nakagami-m/Rayleigh Channels," *Electronics*, vol. 8, pp. 1-14, 2019.
- [7] Nguyen T., Quang Minh T., Tran P., Vozňák M., "Energy Harvesting over Rician Fading Channel: A Performance Analysis for Half-Duplex Bidirectional Sensor Networks under Hardware Impairments," *Sensors*, vol. 18, no. 6, 2018.
- [8] Nguyen Tan N., Tran Hoang Quang Minh, Phuong T., Tran Miroslav Voznak, Tran Trung Duy, Thanh-Long Nguyen, and Phu Tran Tin, "Performance Enhancement for Energy Harvesting Based Two-way Relay Protocols in Wireless Ad-hoc Networks with Partial and Full Relay Selection Methods," *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 84, pp. 178-187, 2019.
- [9] Liu, Ruoheng, Ivana Maric, Predrag Spasojevic, and Roy D. Yates, "Discrete Memoryless Interference and Broadcast Channels with Confidential Messages: Secrecy Rate Regions," *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 54, no. 6, pp. 2493-2507, 2008.
- [10] P. K. Gopala, L. Lai and H. El Gamal, "On the Secrecy Capacity of Fading Channels," *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 54, no. 10, pp. 4687-4698, 2008.
- [11] Sun Li, and Qinghe Du, "A Review of Physical Layer Security Techniques for Internet of Things: Challenges and Solutions," *Entropy*, vol. 20, no. 10, pp. 1-21, 2018.
- [12] Kuhestani Ali, Abbas Mohammadi, and Mohammadali Mohammadi, "Joint Relay Selection and Power Allocation in Large-Scale MIMO Systems with Untrusted Relays and Passive Eavesdroppers," *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 341-355, 2017.
- [13] Hu Lin, Hong Wen, Bin Wu, Fei Pan, Run-Fa Liao, Huanhuan Song, Jie Tang, and Xiumin Wang, "Cooperative Jamming for Physical Layer Security Enhancement in Internet of Things," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 219-228, 2018.
- [14] Tin Phu Tran, Dang The Hung, Tan Nguyen, Tran Duy, and Miroslav Voznak, "Secrecy Performance Enhancement for Underlay Cognitive Radio Networks Employing Cooperative Multi-Hop Transmission with and without Presence of Hardware Impairments," *Entropy*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 1-16, 2019.
- [15] Zhao R., Yuan Y., Fan L., He Y. C., "Secrecy Performance Analysis of Cognitive Decode-and-Forward Relay Networks in Nakagami-m Fading Channels," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 549-563, 2017.
- [16] Tin Phu, Pham Minh Nam, Tran Trung Duy, Phuong Tran, and Miroslav Voznak, "Secrecy Performance of TAS/SC-Based Multi-Hop Harvest-to-Transmit Cognitive WSNs under Joint Constraint of Interference and Hardware Imperfection," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 5, pp. 1-20, 2019.
- [17] Hieu T. D., Duy T. T., Kim B. S., "Performance Enhancement for Multi-hop Harvest-to-Transmit WSNs with Path-Selection Methods in Presence of Eavesdroppers and Hardware Noises," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol 18, no. 12, pp. 5173-5186, 2018.
- [18] Van-Duc Phan, Tan N. Nguyen, Minh Tran, Thanh-Long Nguyen, "Outage probability analysis of dual energy harvesting relay network over rayleigh fading channel using SC and MRC technique," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 803-811, November 2019.
- [19] Tan N. Nguyen, Minh Tran, Van-Duc Phan, Hoang-Nam Nguyen and Thanh-Long Nguyen, "Outage probability analysis of EH relay-assisted non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) systems over block Rayleigh fading channel," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 3607-3614, Oct.2019.
- [20] Caijun Zhong, Himal A. Suraweera, Gan Zheng, Ioannis Krikidis, Zhaoyang Zhang, "Wireless Information and Power Transfer with Full Duplex Relaying," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 2, no. 10, pp. 3447-3461, 2014.
- [21] Nguyen Tan N., Phuong T. Tran, and Miroslav Vozňák, "Power Splitting-based Energy-harvesting Protocol for Wireless-powered Communication Networks with a Bidirectional Relay," *International Journal of Communication Systems*, vol. 31, no. 13, 2018.
- [22] Bhatnagar M. R., "On the Capacity of Decode-and-Forward Relaying over Rician Fading Channels," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 1100-1103, 2013.
- [23] Daniel Zwillinger; "Table of Integrals, Series, and Products," *Academic Press*, Springer: NY, USA, 2015.
- [24] Nasir A. A., Zhou X., Durrani S., Kennedy R. A., "Relaying Protocols for Wireless Energy Harvesting and Information Processing," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 12, no. 7, pp. 3622-3636, 2013.
- [25] Tan N., Nguyen T. H. Q., Minh P., Tran T., Voznak M., "Adaptive Energy Harvesting Relaying Protocol for Two-Way Half Duplex System Network over Rician Fading Channels," *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*, pp. 1-10, 2018.
- [26] Phu Tran Tin, Minh Tran, Tan N. Nguyen and Tran Thanh Trang, "Energy Harvesting Half-Duplex AF Power Splitting Protocol Relay Network over Rician Channel in Case of Maximizing Capacity", *TELKOMNIKA Telecommunication Computing Electronics and Control*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 1615-1624, August, 2019.
- [27] Phu Tran Tin, T.H.Q.Minh, Tan N. Nguyen and Thanh-Long Nguyen, "A new look at energy harvesting half-duplex DF power splitting protocol relay network over Rician channel in case of maximizing capacity", *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 249-257, January 2019.